

Utilizing a Blockchain for Managing Sensor Metadata in Exposure Health Studies

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Abstract— Commercial Internet of Things (IoT) sensors enable continuous data collection that benefits exposomic studies. The Exposure Health Informatics Ecosystem (EHIE) is one such sensor-based informatics platform for performing multiple simultaneous exposomic studies. It captures data from networks of sensors designed to record air quality in homes of the study’s participants and neighboring areas. In such cases where sensors are continually streaming data, it is crucial to monitor, in real time, the operational status of the network and record possible anomalies. Data collected by these sensors is only useful if it is free of errors. Therefore, maintaining the proper integrity of devices requires the capture of all deployment events that can cause anomalies. Tracking faults by recording system metadata is a difficult task, and we need a mechanism to capture the trajectories of devices within and across studies, systematically capture metadata of deployed version, and assign appropriate provenance to data recorded from each sensor. In this paper, we propose the use of a permissioned blockchain to manage the metadata and connect seemingly unrelated changes to create a trajectory of events that could result in the errors we observe. We implement a preliminary version of our blockchain solution in Hyperledger Fabric to help track errors in such a volatile setup. We also highlight how the properties of blockchain fulfill the essential needs for a metadata management solution needed in our case study.

Keywords— Air Quality Sensors, exposure Health Informatics Ecosystem, internet of things, hyperledger fabric.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many areas of translational biomedical research have profited from commercial Internet of Things (IoT) sensors that enable continuous data collection. However, these IoT devices are prone to failures and network interruptions, in part due to their low cost. Usually, these devices make up the end nodes of a network that are recording physiological and environmental data of research participants. In such cases where sensors are continually streaming data, it is crucial to monitor, in real time, the operational status of the network and record possible anomalies. Data collected by these sensors is only useful if it is free of errors such as those of associating data streams with a

wrong study participant, and data loss from when a sensor was offline.

The Exposure Health Informatics Ecosystem (EHIE) is a sensor-based informatics platform for performing exposure health studies [1–3]. It includes a Data Acquisition Platform, EpiFi [4, 5], that captures data from networks of sensors designed to record air quality in homes of the study’s participants and neighboring areas along with their physiological status. This platform includes hardware and software tools, wireless networking, and protocols to support easy sensor system deployment and robust sensor data collection. EpiFi interacts with participant facing tools and central big data integration components of the ecosystem to systematically integrate sensor recordings with patient-reported and clinical data for researchers to perform study analysis. EpiFi has been evaluated in different types of sensor deployment designs to accommodate several clinical study designs, including: (1) High-resolution air sensing [6], (2) Automation of interventions [6], (3) Requisition of clinical status, feedback and activity annotation [7], and (4) Acquisition of heterogeneous sensor data from participant homes [4, 5].

Sensor-based exposure health studies have different study designs [8] that require different sensor deployment designs. They range from having a few participants with multiple sensors to those with participants in order of a few tens with 2 to 5 sensors to those that enroll hundreds for participants with usually a single sensor. In all these designs, it is essential to capture and share contextual information of individual sensor deployments, for triggering participant related events and integrate with collected data, to support robust study analysis. To gather this information, we developed a sensor metadata specification that describes the metadata needed to be captured in these studies [9] and implemented a repository for deployment metadata within EpiFi [4, 5].

Low-cost IoT devices and sensors are prone to failures and require constant maintenance, including repeated cleaning and calibration. Such intervention can result in changes to the configuration and potentially cause errors in the readings. In its

life-cycle, a device could be swapped among study subjects, assigned to a new study subject, undergo remote or on-premise maintenance and updates, and possibly discarded if it is beyond repair. A deployer might want to record what has been done to fix a particular sensor, such as replacing a component. Tracking this information is paramount to understanding the life-cycle of a sensor. However, there is no obvious place to put this information. Sensor readings can be mislabeled when a device is redeployed to a new participant's home, and the recorded measurements are associated with the wrong participant due to human error. The EHIE ecosystem also supports multiple simultaneous studies, and sensors could be assigned across these studies. These deployments use different configurations and software versions. Therefore, maintaining the proper integrity of assigned devices requires the capture of all these deployment events that can cause these anomalies. There is no precise mechanism to detect and record different, seemingly unrelated events efficiently. Various users of EHIE also have different access policies. For example, a person responsible for deploying a sensor should be able to update certain information about the sensor, such as its location. However, they should not be able to update other sensor information, such as its firmware version. Thus, the identity of the trigger and source of each incident must be recorded correctly. Also, the private data of the participants needs to be handled carefully. However, there is no way to record and track who has exported data from the system. Tracking faults by recording system metadata is a difficult task, and we need a mechanism to capture the trajectories of devices within and across studies, systematically capture metadata of deployed version, and assign appropriate provenance to data recorded from each sensor.

Blockchain is emerging as a popular solution for efficient management of patient data used in medical research [10–13]. Blockchain is a distributed, tamper-proof, append-only ledger which provides a highly available storage solution that we use to efficiently log metadata for reads and writes of the sensor data and all system updates. The updates to the metadata are propagated in order and are easy to audit, which we use to trace faults. Since this approach provides us a tamper-proof log, we do not need additional effort to handle any inadvertent errors that may be introduced if we use other distributed storage solutions. However, popular public blockchain networks, such as Bitcoin [14], are usually hard to scale and involve algorithms such as Proof-of-Work for maintaining consensus that requires high computing power. Such high overheads are unfavorable as IoT devices have limited resources.

In this paper, we propose the use of a permissioned blockchain to manage the metadata and address the limitations and requirements listed above. Given the closed group of participants, instead of using a compute-heavy Proof-of-Work algorithm, we use a less complex Byzantine consensus algorithm. We assign access policies to the different users of the EHIE system. Smart contracts are used to automate the detection and logging of any relevant events and define policies to handle authentication efficiently to restrict access to participants' private data such as their location, activities, etc. Furthermore, we connect these seemingly unrelated changes to create a trajectory of events that could result in the errors we observe.

This trace is analyzed to identify the source of an error we observe or for any auditing.

To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first application of blockchain for an IoT-based exposomic study with fine-granular access control to perform operations involving sensitive data. We implement a preliminary version of our blockchain solution in Hyperledger Fabric [15] to help track errors in a volatile setup. We also highlight how the properties of blockchain fulfill the essential needs for a metadata management solution needed in our case study. Other cases of mobile or IoT-driven biomedical research share some of the same challenges as our study; hence, our blockchain-based solution is likely to be widely applicable. The logging mechanism described here would be relevant to other systems as well, irrespective of the events that result in the errors. Authentication and access control are essential components of our solution as there are different organizations involved in a study, and the participants' data is sensitive.

In the rest of this paper, we provide details about constructing a blockchain network in Section 2 and our air monitoring experimental setup in Section 3. Next, we discuss our proposed design and how our solution meets the requirements of the system in Section 4. In Section 5, we describe the implementation of our blockchain network and then discuss some future work directions in Section 6. Section 7 points to other existing works that use blockchain to manage medical data. Finally, we conclude the paper in Section 8.

II. BLOCKCHAIN

A. Blockchain Network

Blockchain is a distributed append-only ledger that is easy to verify. Each participating peer in the blockchain protocol is associated with an asymmetric key pair and has a view of the current state. Thus, there is no dependence on a single server, which could be a point of failure. Even in the case of network partitions, peers can log events which can be propagated to others and merged with the global state on reconnection. A peer compiles a block of transactions and broadcasts it to the network. Each block also contains the hash pointer to the last block in the blockchain [16]. The actions performed by the peer nodes is governed by smart contracts that can be used to automate metadata management efficiently. To incorporate multi-party management by providing policies to control the kind of access allowed to different users of the system.

Nakamoto's cryptocurrency application, Bitcoin [14] popularized the use of blockchain. Since then, blockchain has been a useful tool in various industries. Section 7 lists some applications of blockchain in healthcare and medical research.

Depending on the trust model among the participants, there are two types of blockchain networks - public and permissioned. In the case of a public blockchain, like Bitcoin, anyone is allowed to participate in the network and consensus is achieved using algorithms like Proof-of-Work. Whereas, in a permissioned blockchain, there is a known set of participants that follow traditional BFT consensus. We use a permissioned blockchain platform, Hyperledger Fabric [15] to implement the blockchain network.

B. Hyperledger Fabric

Hyperledger Fabric [15] is a platform for permissioned blockchains that provide the flexibility to incorporate different membership policies and consensus algorithms. A smart contract is known as the chaincode in Fabric. Each peer has access to the chaincode, that executes in a separate docker container and a local ledger as a snapshot of the current state of the blockchain. A Peer Transaction Manager maintains the state of the blockchain in a versioned key-value store. A membership service provider node is responsible for assigning cryptographic identities to the peers of the network.

Fabric follows an execute-order-validate architecture. First, in the execution phase, the peer proposing the update cryptographically signs and sends the query to a group of nodes for endorsement. The endorsers execute the operation they receive on the specified chaincode based on their local state. If successful, they generate a read set, which is the version of the database before the execution of the query and a write set, which is the updated state after execution. The endorser sends a signed endorsement as the proposal response containing the read and write sets, the transaction ID, and the endorser ID. The proposing peer waits for the required endorsements and then sends a transaction to the ordering nodes containing the proposal along with the endorsements. Next, in the ordering phase, the ordering nodes receive transactions from various peers and establish consensus on their order and batch them into blocks. These blocks are broadcast to all the peers of the blockchain using gossip protocol. The number of nodes, the endorsement policy, and consensus protocol used in the ordering service are pluggable modules. Finally, in the validation phase, as peers receive blocks, they validate the transactions, check for read-write conflicts, and update their state accordingly. Along with this active method of replication, Fabric also uses primary-backup as a passive replication technique to keep nodes up to date on the current state of the blockchain.

III. AIR QUALITY SENSING NETWORK

Fig. 1. High-resolution air quality sensing in-home deployment

A combination of stationary and mobile sensors measure the air quality in study participants’ environments. Depending on the study requirements, EpiFi is capable of acquiring data from sensor networks having different designs and triggering various participant related activities. Figure 1 shows an example of high-resolution air quality sensing with eight stationary sensors deployed across and outside a participant home. The stationary sensors installed in the participant’s home are connected to the

home’s WiFi access point and a gateway to connect the sensors to the server recording the air quality measurements.

Fig. 2. Interventions and additional data requisition orchestrated by EpiFi. (Top) Air quality sensors triggering a furnace fan and a thermostat. (Bottom) Ecological momentary assessments triggered by air quality levels.

The goal of continuous sensing is (1) to generate an air quality exposure profile of the study participants, and (2) to trigger interventions or request additional information from participants (clinical status, feedback, and activity annotation). These together are used for study analysis. Based on the air quality, the gateway can trigger interventions by turning on devices in the home like the furnace fan and thermostat, as shown in Figure 2a. Participants also receive direct feedback when air pollution levels change, and they can respond with the activities that might have caused the reported reading. Figure 2b shows this text interface. Different commercial IoT devices, including motion sensors, door sensors, etc., and tracking participant’s smartphones, are used to sense their location and obtain other environmental parameters at participant homes. Figure 3 shows the sample interface of various deployments.

Deployments of sensors for any study design involves multiple steps. Steps involving sensor and acquisition platform deployment are accompanied with metadata capture. These include sensor identifiers, locations, and maintenance and calibration events. Current deployments of EHIE include (1) 2 to 5 sensors for 10 participants for a pilot study supported by PRISMS, and (2) a single sensor each for 100 participants in the Environmental influences on Child Health Outcomes (ECHO) study [7]. Deployment metadata captured at these scales, which is usually through manual inputs, is prone to errors, especially those involving changes to initially deployed sensors. To be able to track any faults that occur in the system, some critical events

identified are the status of the sensors, location of sensors, firmware updates, and other maintenance interruptions.

Fig. 3. Multiple sensors deployment interface.

Also, there is a need for differential access to data and metadata generated within EHIE. While the primary research team has complete access to the data for the study, there is a need to minimize exposure of protected health information to those not requiring it and for many secondary users of the data. Also, by design, the research administrative team that manages the infrastructure has access to the data or potential unintended changes to recorded data need to be minimized. Currently, some of the system changes are manually uploaded in a separate server, and there are no access and update policies in place for the different users of the system. Using a centralized architecture to maintain metadata in a highly unreliable system proves challenging.

IV. METADATA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

A. System Design

The blockchain network consists of a group of servers that interact with the existing air monitoring network, as shown in Figure 4. We identify four interfaces required between these networks to capture the events described in Section 3. The peers in the blockchain network act based on (1) changes at the gateway capturing events based on the sensor’s status (Sensor Subscriber), (2) the interface used by researchers to extract data (Data Exporter), (3) the interface used for system maintenance (System Maintenance), and (4) an interface to up- date offline or manual updates (Manual Updates Dashboard). The commands on these interfaces trigger the smart contracts on the blockchain peer nodes to invoke a transaction on the blockchain. They also update different fields of the metadata depending on the events recorded at the interface. The Sensor Subscriber records changes to the status of the sensors, for instance, when the sensor goes offline. The Data Exporter organization logs whenever a peer reads the sensor data. The System Maintenance organization nodes trigger a transaction for any firmware updates or maintenance operations. Lastly, any changes to the sensor that requires manual intervention such as, installing new deployments, need to be entered through a dashboard. The queries invoked on the system can perform basic operations such as adding a new sensor, reading the metadata of the sensor, and updating a sensor’s metadata. A query that triggers an insert or update in the ledger returns a success message when the initiating peer receives a successful commit. An update is not considered committed until this point. In case of a failure

message, the update requires the EHIE node to reissue the triggering operation.

The roles of the users of the study helped define the trust boundaries. The sensor node can only perform updates, and researchers can only perform reads. However, the maintenance nodes can read and update the metadata but do not have access

Fig. 4. Blockchain-based metadata management system design.

to sensitive information. Within each trust boundary, there are additional hierarchical access policies; for instance, a peer from the infrastructure node would need approval before making a firmware change.

To complete the tracking system, we need to derive a trace of all the metadata updates related to a sensor over time and record them in order. Finally, when we observe an error in a sensor’s readings, we can query the trajectory of the metadata updates for further analysis.

B. Blockchain Properties for Metadata Management

The blockchain network is operated by a group of nodes, each containing the snapshot of the state of the system. This local ledger enables us to query the system state from any peer we connect to with high availability. The access control policy in the chaincode checks if the node belonging to the infrastructure organization is trying to access the system state. Various other properties of the blockchain discussed next help us build a reliable system. The local ledger at each peer gets updated using the active and passive replication schemes described in Section 2. Each transaction executed is signed by the peer that proposed the query, the endorsers, and the ordering nodes. These signatures help us verify the integrity of the updates propagated. Finally, since each block points to the previous block, each update to the metadata of a sensor can be traced in the order that the changes occurred. Easy verification at the peer nodes is used to ensure the correctness of the results returned from a query execution. Therefore, we have achieved availability, access control, reliable fault tracking with the use of blockchain.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Using Hyperledger Fabric, we implement the three categories of participants of our study as three different organizations. Within these organizations, there can be multiple nodes that act as the peer nodes in the blockchain network. Each organization is in the same trust domain. In our case, we have two nodes for each organization to cover all test scenarios.

Figure 5 shows the access policies defined for Sensor Subscriber nodes.

```

Policies:
  Readers:
    Type: Signature
    Rule: "OR('Org1MSP.admin', 'Org1MSP.peer', 'Org1MSP.client')"
  Writers:
    Type: Signature
    Rule: "OR('Org1MSP.admin', 'Org1MSP.client')"
  Admins:
    Type: Signature
    Rule: "OR('Org1MSP.admin')"
```

Fig. 5. Access policies for nodes in the sensor subscriber organization.

We create separate docker containers to run each node and to run the associated chaincode. This separation ensures the desired isolation between the nodes and the respective chaincode execution environment. We implemented the chaincode in Golang, and the communication across the containers uses the gRPC framework. The fields required to capture the metadata for a given sensor, as shown in Figure 6, need to be marshaled as JSON objects. Figure 7 shows a snippet of a sample query implemented in the smart contract. The *Invoke* function is the API used by the peer to trigger any operation in the smart contract.

```

type Metadata struct {
  SensorId string `json:"sensorId"`
  SensorName string `json:"sensorName"`
  Location string `json:"location"`
  Builder string `json:"builder"`
  BuildDate string `json:"buildDate"`
  DeploymentData string `json:"deploymentData"`
  Deployer string `json:"deployer"`
  Measurement string `json:"measurement"`
  CalibrationCurve string `json:"caliberationCurve"`
  CaliberationData string `json:"caliberationData"`
  Event string `json:"event"`
  Notes string `json:"notes"`
}
```

Fig. 4. Sensor metadata fields

All peer nodes perform both endorsements and commit operations. The current endorsement policy requires a majority. This policy can be altered based on rules within an organization or based on a query. There is currently only one node that orders the transactions, which is the Solo ordering service module in Hyperledger Fabric. This module is sufficient for our preliminary implementation of the solution. However, for a more comprehensive implementation, we propose using a Byzantine consensus module which is already supported by Fabric. Moreover, Fabric's design allows us to add nodes in the ordering service and change the ordering protocol without altering the rest of the network.

VI. FUTURE WORK

In the current implementation of the blockchain network, all peers in an organization are within the same trust boundary. For this use case, we need to add more fine-grained access policies to differentiate the specific roles within each organization, as described in Section 4. For more practical privacy preservation, we must restrict access to fields of the metadata recorded as well.

A thorough performance testing of the blockchain network is required as more sensors get deployed. The challenges we might face to accommodate the throughput in large scale deployments, e.g., a city-wide deployment, are not clear. We anticipate that there might be a need to add a preprocessing step

before transactions are triggered in the blockchain network to reduce its load and thereby control any increase in latency.

```

Func (s *SmartContract) Invoke(APIStub shim.ChaincodeStubInterface) sc.Response {
  // Retrieve the requested Smart Contract function and arguments
  function, args := APIStub.GetFunctionAndParameters()
  // Route to the appropriate handler function to interact with the ledger appropriately
  if function == "querySensor" {
    return s.querySensor(APIStub, args)
  } else if function == "initLedger" {
    return s.initLedger(APIStub)
  } else if function == "createSensor" {
    return s.createSensor(APIStub)
  } else if function == "updateMetadata" {
    return s.updateMetadata(APIStub, args)
  }
  return shim.Error("Invalid Smart Contract function name.")
}

Func (s *SmartContract) querySensor(APIStub shim.ChaincodeStubInterface, args []string)
sc.Response {
  if len(args) != 1 {
    return shim.Error("Incorrect number of arguments. Expecting 1")
  }
  sensorAsBytes, _ := APIStub.GetState(args[0])
  return shim.Success(sensorAsBytes)
}
```

Fig. 7. Snippet of a samples smart contract.

The different studies based on the data collected by the sensors can also benefit from each other. We want to explore how the blockchain can be used to share the conclusions from the individual studies without necessarily sharing the raw data, thereby preserving the privacy of the participants' data. We also continue assessments of this prototype for other commonly used proofs (Proof of Work, Proof of Stake, Proof of Hold, Delegated Proof of Stake, Proof of Capacity, and Proof of Elapsed Time) leveraged in IoT implementations and specifically for biomedical use cases [16].

VII. RELATED WORK

Blockchain has most commonly proposed to improve the interoperability of electronic health records (EHR) [12, 17–20]. A blockchain-based data preservation system proposed in [17] describes an automated, decentralized, and tamper-proof solution for reliable storage of medical data while also preserving privacy. The work in [18] uses attribute-based cryptography along with blockchain to achieve confidentiality, integrity of medical data, and support for fine-grained access control. Data consumers can access medical data based on the access policy defined by patients and encrypted hospital records. Shared keys are generated from the patient's identity information using identity-based cryptography. Additionally, this solution can be incorporated for medical insurance claims. Privacy of EHR data when shared among different parties is emphasized in [19]. Their solution requires sharing the encryption key with the parties interested in the data, while there is no secure method to provide and revoke this access. Interoperability among hospitals also facilitates precise medicine development by pharmaceutical scientists [12].

Similar management of medical data is required in other domains of biomedicine as well. A study based on genomic data [10] faces governance challenges that they propose to solve by storing data ownership or viewership permissions on-chain. Governance is a broad problem in the drug supply chain that is addressed in [21]. A complete data marketplace solution was proposed by [11] where participants can share their data with healthcare professionals and researchers in a secure platform without exposing their information.

Location privacy is also a focus in similar use cases like telecare medical information system [22], and remote patient

monitoring [19]. Multi-level privacy is achieved in [22] by utilizing order-preserving encryption. Depending on the organization's purpose for accessing the patient's location, a different size of the area is returned. This solution is, however, not applicable to our use case considering the scale and focus of the study.

VIII. CONCLUSION

We begin with exploring the challenges of our Exposure Health Informatics Ecosystem built to conduct experiments using air quality sensors. We highlight the main challenge of metadata management when dealing with large and volatile IoT networks. In our approach, we identify the sources of errors and anomalies that can occur during data collection and use a blockchain-based management system to log these events. Then we present our preliminary implementation of the blockchain network to show the use of our proposed solution. We also argue that our system is effective in handling a wide range of IoT-based biomedical research. Finally, we present a roadmap of the improvements we need to make to complete our solution.

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